

CHOOSING THE TYPE OF MACHINE ROLLER WHICH WILL PROVIDE TRACK WORK TO PLOWED LANDS

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Abstract. Based on the analysis of the literature carried out in order to select the optimal type of the roller, the planar roller was selected for use in the combined machine through the results of the comparative tests of the planar, toothed planar and rod roller.

Keywords. Roller, Plank, Gear Plank, Rod, Frame, Vertical Compressive Strength, Flattener, Crushing, Density, Tensile Strength

In order to carry out comparative tests, the same 40 cm diameter, 1.5 m coverage width, plate, toothed plate and wire coils and a special frame (laboratory-field device) on which they are installed were developed, and experimental copies of them were prepared. The working parts of the developed coils were described. . The laboratory-field device was designed to allow for the installation of different types of coils and the ability to vary the vertical pressure applied to them over a wide range.

Comparative trials were conducted in a post-harvest wheat field that was irrigated and plowed and surfaced with a machine equipped with disc rollers and a leveler.

Tests were conducted in the third and fourth gears of the MTZ-80 tractor. As evaluation criteria, the compaction quality of the soil in the 0-10 cm layer, its density, and the tensile strength of the rollers were taken. The compaction quality, density, and tensile strength of the soil were determined.

Results of comparative tests of different coils

Type of roller	The amount of fractions of the following size (mm), %			Soil density, g/cm ³	Rollers tensile strength, N/m
	>50	50-25	<25		
V=6,2 km/hour					
Planked	6,8	9,2	84,0	1,24	202
Cogged planked	3,4	7,2	89,4	1,22	228
Rodded	9,6	9,1	81,3	1,25	193

V=8,3 km/hour					
Planked	5,9	6,7	87,4	1,21	246
Cooged planked	2,3	6,1	91,6	1,20	247
Rodded	9,5	7,8	82,7	1,22	218

According to the results obtained in the tests, the following can be noted:

- in terms of the soil compaction quality, the toothed plate roller has higher indicators compared to the plate and rod rollers. A roller with a rod and a plate grinds the pieces a little worse than it. As a result, the amount of fractions smaller than 25 mm is 8.1-8.9 and 4.2-5.4 percent less, respectively, when processed with wire and plate rollers, and the amount of fractions larger than 50 mm is less than when processed with toothed plate rollers. 6.2 -7.2 and 3.4-3.6 percent more;
- the density of the soil was almost the same in all three coils;
- to draw a roller with a toothed plate according to the results of tensometry the largest, and the coil with the wire provided the least resistance. This can be explained by the difference in the depth of their immersion in the soil.

It is understood that the toothed plate roller is sunk deeper into the soil, while the rod roller is sunk shallower.

The increase in the speed of the unit from 6.2 km/h to 8.3 km/h led to the improvement of the quality of soil compaction, decrease in density, and increase in the traction resistance of the rollers.

The plow is equipped only with disk rollers and a leveler, that is, when working with a machine without rollers, the soil does not meet the requirements for the planting background in terms of the quality of soil compaction, density and leveling of the surface part.

It became clear from the observations that after passing the plate and toothed plate rollers, a soft layer of 3-4 cm thickness was formed on the field surface, which ensures the preservation of moisture in the soil. Based on the above-mentioned, if the combined machine used in row cultivation of plowed land is installed with a roller with a toothed plate, the preservation of soil moisture is performed at the required level. In addition, good soil compaction was observed.

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